

ANALYSIS OF ALGORITHMS FOR PREDICTING THE PROBABILITY OF FATAL OUTCOME IN PATIENTS AFTER MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Abstract. *This paper examines various algorithms for predicting the probability of death in patients who have had a myocardial infarction. Classical statistical models, machine learning algorithms, and hybrid models for factor risk analysis are considered. Using these algorithms allows providing patients with individual medical care.*

Keywords: *Myocardial infarction, machine learning, hybrid models, logistic regression, artificial neural networks, time series, laboratory results, personalized prognosis.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуются различные алгоритмы прогнозирования вероятности летального исхода у пациентов, перенесших инфаркт миокарда. Рассматриваются классические статистические модели, алгоритмы машинного обучения и гибридные модели для анализа факторного риска. Использование данных алгоритмов позволяет обеспечить пациентам индивидуальное медицинское обслуживание.*

Ключевые слова: *инфаркт миокарда, машинное обучение, гибридные модели, логистическая регрессия, искусственные нейронные сети, временные ряды, результаты лабораторных исследований, персонализированный прогноз.*

Introduction

Myocardial infarction is a serious and often fatal disease, and early assessment of the risk of death plays an important role in increasing the patient's chances of survival. With the development of medical technologies, the methods of predicting the probability of death of patients who have experienced a myocardial infarction are improving. Methods ranging from traditional statistical models to modern machine learning algorithms are used in this process. Research shows that these algorithms, based on individual medical data, can help patients choose the most appropriate treatment options, taking into account the complexity of risk factors. This article analyzes in detail the algorithms used to determine the risk of death, their working principles and capabilities based on various models.

Classical statistical models are the first step in predicting the risk of death in patients with myocardial infarction. These models work based on the basic demographic and clinical factors of the patients.

- Logistic regression: Widely used in the analysis of risk factors of patients who have experienced a heart attack. Through logistic regression, indicators such as the patient's age, gender, blood pressure, cholesterol level, and heart rate are associated with the probability of death. This model does not require complex mathematical calculations and its effectiveness has been proven in clinical practice.

- Proportional hazards model (Cox model): This model is used to analyze time-dependent risk factors. For example, if a patient's risk of a heart attack changes over time, the Cox model takes these changes into account. The model allows monitoring of risk among patients over time.

- **Binomial regression and Poisson regression:** These methods are used to analyze the probability of death using numerical or binary variables. For example, the combined effect of a patient's various risk factors can help predict mortality.

These models are simple and provide accurate enough results to make predictions based on patients' risk scores. But they also have their limitations, for example, when working with variables of high complexity or large data sets, these methods may lose their effectiveness.

Methods of diagnosis of myocardial infarction based on machine learning algorithms

Machine learning algorithms are effective in analyzing large amounts of medical data and predicting a patient's risk of death with high accuracy. These algorithms not only identify associations between variables, but also explore complex relationships between them.

- *Random Forests:* Random forests are effective in identifying associations between risk factors at different levels. Using this algorithm, the impact of various parameters on the risk level can be determined. Due to the high flexibility of the model, it maintains high accuracy when working with large data sets.

- *Gradient boosting and XGBoost:* These algorithms allow accurate prediction of mortality risk by sequentially adding a large number of decision trees. These ensemble models have high accuracy in studying medical data, and they provide an opportunity to take into account complex relationships between risk factors.

- *Artificial Neural Networks:* Neural networks are used to analyze large amounts of complex and interconnected data. Model types such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) can help predict mortality risk by examining time-series data. The use of artificial neural networks in the analysis of time-dependent changes in ECG or troponin level makes the results more accurate.

- *Clustering algorithms:* Clustering methods allow patients to be divided into several groups based on their risk factors. With this method, patients with similar risk profiles are accurately predicted and assigned individualized treatment options.

The main advantage of machine learning algorithms is the ability to analyze complex and interconnected risk factors. At the same time, the use of these methods requires high computer resources, and their implementation in medical practice requires a certain level of technical skills.

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Diagnostic methods based on time series algorithms

Time series and dynamic modeling are effective approaches for predicting the probability of death in patients with myocardial infarction. This approach allows monitoring the health indicators of patients over time, which is very important when analyzing time-dependent parameters such as heart rate, blood pressure, and electrocardiography (ECG) data. Autocorrelation and trend analysis are performed using time series. Autocorrelation is a technique used to determine the correlation between data collected over a period of time, which may indicate that health changes have a certain trend. And trend analysis helps to determine the general trend between indicators that change over time. These methods play an important role in determining the dynamics that increase the risk of infarction, for example, time-dependent changes are controlled based on the patient's personal characteristics, lifestyle and medical history.

Dynamic modeling takes into account the time-dependent consequences of changes in the patient's health and other parameters. This approach uses Markov chains and state-transition models. Markov chains help model the transition of a patient's health from one state to another over time. At each stage, the patient's state of health is predicted, and with the help of this sequence of stages, the possibility of long-term prognosis is increased. And state-of-the-art models allow tracking changes between stages of health after a heart attack, such as recovery, risk of recurrence, or disease severity. These approaches are very important in determining the patient's risk of death, as they provide an opportunity to make predictions based on risk factors at each stage.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models provide high accuracy in time series data. These machine learning techniques allow us to observe associations that develop over time, including correlations between a patient's current and previous states. RNN models are very flexible for time series and allow learning of indicators that change over different time periods. And LSTM models are used to remember long-term changes and reduce uncertainties in time series, which is important in analyzing ECG data and monitoring various heart functions. The complexity of these models also ensures high accuracy in determining dynamic changes in the patient's health indicators.

The practical use of time series and dynamic modeling is very important in determining the risk of death and developing individual treatment plans for patients who have experienced a heart attack. Through these approaches, information about patients' health indicators and risk factors is monitored in real time, and individualized treatment methods are applied according to the patient's risk level. At the same time, through the widespread use of time series and dynamic modeling, the possibility of introducing advanced technologies and algorithms in the medical field will increase, which will create more effective and faster treatment options for patients. As a result, time series and dynamic modeling play an important role in determining the risk of death of patients who have experienced a heart attack, applying individualized treatment methods, and implementing the latest advances in medical practice.

Conclusions

Algorithms for predicting the risk of death in patients who have had a myocardial infarction are important in determining the treatment plan. Research shows that the effective use of classical statistical models, machine learning, and hybrid approaches yields excellent results in identifying risk factors and recommending appropriate treatment to patients. This article analyzes each of the death prediction algorithms and provides recommendations for their use in medicine.

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